

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Toshboyeva Hurshida Farhod qizi

AUTOCAD DASTURIDA 2D MODILING KO'RINISHIDAN 3D MODILING

KO'RINISHIGA O'TISH

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

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